

Studies of Heterocyclic Compounds with Pharmacological Possibilities: 2-Nitrophenylbenzofuran

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Several 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans have been synthesised by cyclisation of 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes, obtained by the interaction of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehydes and *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide.

In earlier papers communicated from these laboratories, preparation of uroyl benzofurans¹ and 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans² has been described. The studies have now been extended to certain 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans required for some pharmacological investigations.

It has been observed that a mixture of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide, and freshly ignited potassium carbonate in ethanol, on being refluxed for about half an hour, yields the respective 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes. The 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes readily furnish oxime derivatives and undergo cyclisation to the respective 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans, when treated with ethanolic potassium hydroxide. The cyclisation is smooth with almost quantitative yields.

The 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes are crystalline solids, insoluble in water, and soluble in ethanol and acetic acid. These do not show colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid. The 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans are coloured crystalline solids, insoluble in water, not very much soluble in ethanol and acetic acid. They exhibit halochromism with concentrated sulphuric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Hydroxyaldehydes.—2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-, -4-methyl-, -3-chloro-, -5-chloro-, -5-bromo-, and -4,5-dimethyl-benzaldehydes were synthesised by the improved Duff reaction³.

2-*p*-Nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes.—A mixture of *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.05 *M*), 4-nitrobenzyl bromide (0.05 *M*), and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (0.08 *M*) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 45 minutes with constant shaking and cooled. The precipitated solid was filtered and washed with dilute ethanol and then with water. Recrystallisation of the product from acetic acid gave the respective 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes. The compounds prepared and their oxime derivatives are recorded in Table I.

1. Singh and Kapil, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 24, 2064; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 695.

2. Singh and Verma, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 49.

3. Liggett and Diehl, *Proc. Iowa Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 52, 191.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.P.	2-p-Nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehydes.		Corresponding oximes.				
					Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	%Nitrogen.
1	H	H	H	118°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	C : 65.1% H : 4.3	C : 65.3% 4.3	183°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂	10.2	10.3
2	Me	H	H	121°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	C : 66.0 H : 4.7	C : 66.4 4.8	149°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	9.8	9.8
3	H	H	Me	100°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	C : 65.7 H : 4.5	C : 66.4 4.8	150°	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	9.9	9.8
4	H	Me	Me	128°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	C : 67.9 H : 5.2	C : 67.4 5.3	151°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	9.2	9.3
5	H	H	Cl	165°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ NCl	Cl : 12.0	Cl : 12.2	180°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	9.1	9.2
6	H	H	Br	160°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ NBr	Br : 23.5	Br : 23.8	170°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂ Br	8.1	8.0

N.B. The aldehydes were crystallised from glacial acetic acid and the oximes, from ethanol. The aldehydes and the oxides are all colorless.

TABLE II

2-p-Nitrophenylbenzofurans.

Sl.No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Colour.	M.P.	Solvent cryst. from.	Colour with H ₂ SO ₄ .	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1*	H	H	H	Yellow needles	182°	Acetic acid	Violet-brown	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N	C : 71.1% H : 3.7	70.3% 3.8
2	H	H	Me	Light orange-yellow	265°	Abs. ethanol+acetic acid	Light blue-black, turning dark	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	C : 70.8 H : 4.3	71.1 4.4
3**	H	H	Me	Pale yellow flakes	180°	Ethanol	Deep violet tan	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	C : 70.6 H : 4.4	71.1 4.4
4	Me	H	H	Yellow needles	180°	Do	Brown, turning black	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ N	C : 71.6 H : 4.3	71.1 4.4
5	Me	Me	H	Orange-yellow	211°	Abs. ethanol+acetic acid	Violet-red turning dark	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	C : 72.5 H : 4.8	71.9 4.9
6**	H	H	Cl	Light tan	245°	Do	Light brown, turning dark	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ NCl	C : 60.8 H : 2.9	61.4 2.9
7	Cl	H	H	Yellow needles	195°	Ethanol	Pale yellow, turning brown	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ NCl	C : 61.9 H : 2.8	61.4 2.9
8	Br	H	H	Yellow	196°	Abs. ethanol+acetic acid	Violet, turning brown	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ NBr	Br : 24.8	25.2

*Mishra and Mehra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1954.

**The intermediate 2-p-nitrobenzyloxy derivative has not been isolated in pure state.

2-p-Nitrophenylbenzofurans.—To a solution of KOH (1.0 g.) in ethanol (15.0 ml) was added 2-*p*-nitrobenzyloxybenzaldehyde (2.0 g.) and the mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 25 minutes (the colorless reaction mixture gradually changed to a dark colour). It was cooled and the precipitated solid was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds prepared are recorded in Table II.

When moistened with H₂SO₄ (conc.), the 2-*p*-nitrophenylbenzofurans exhibit halochromism.

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